

Training and Research in Analytical Chemistry : An Interdisciplinary Science

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A brief survey of the work being pursued in India in the discipline of analytical chemistry has been presented. The need of developing novel directions of approach and the use of more sophisticated techniques has been highlighted. Research work in the field of analytical chemistry should be accompanied by a clear understanding of the tools, the limits of precision involved and the basic chemical principles of the process. There should be an active coordination between teaching and research.

It is a matter of great pleasure for me to contribute this article to the special issue of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society, being brought out on the occasion of the sixtieth birthday of my friend Professor Arun K. Dey. Prof. Dey's outstanding contributions in the field of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, ranging over approximately four decades, are too well known to be enumerated here. Beginning with novel methods¹ of calculation of formation constants of complex ions, Prof. Dey has made significant contributions in the fields of coordination chemistry of lanthanides² and inorganic polymers³; the applications of inorganic concepts to analytical chemistry has been his abiding interest and has resulted in internationally recognised contributions from his research school in the fields of chromatography⁴, ion exchange⁵, electrophoresis⁶, ring oven technique⁷, ion selective electrodes⁸ and spectrophotometric determination of metal ions⁹. In view of his keen interest in teaching and research in analytical chemistry, it appears appropriate to present in this article a brief account of the development of this interdisciplinary field of science.

Analytical chemistry may be defined as the science of chemical characterization and measurement. With the merging boundaries of conventionally accepted disciplines of science, the meaning of the term *chemical characterization* has been changing and now covers many techniques which would have at one time been considered to belong to the domain of physical analysis or biological assay. Simultaneously, the instruments with which measurements are made have been constantly undergoing development. Efforts at improvements in the techniques of characterization and measurements to incorporate more and more complex situations (e.g., ultramicro quantities in large interfering preponderances) constitute major thrusts of research in analytical chemistry. However, fundamental progress in these demanding sophisticated techniques does require a very clear understanding of the theoretical principles involved. In addition, the analytical chemist in his efforts to enlarge the utility of the applications of his science for different disciplines (e.g., meteorology, geology and biology) has to develop a better

appreciation of the specific needs of these users and make the analytical procedures as foolproof as possible for those who are not highly trained in analytical chemistry.

Conversely, many types of scientists (including chemists of different specialisations) and engineers have been continuously making valuable contributions to analytical chemistry. A physical chemist, for example, may spend some time and effort in improving the time-, spatial- or frequency-resolution of his spectroscopic measurements to draw more reliable and penetrating conclusions in his current area of research. What distinguishes an analytical chemist is that he makes improvements in characterization and measurements his goal rather than means to an end.

Growth of analytical chemistry and India's contribution to the field: In his thought provoking special award address at the Society for Analytical Chemists at Pittsburgh in 1980, H. A. Laitinen¹⁰ presented a graphic account of the phenomenal growth and importance of 'Analytical Chemistry in a Changing World', which makes it clear that analytical chemistry continues to occupy a central place in the overall growth of chemistry. This is depicted by the data in Table 1¹¹ representing the percentage of chemical publications which were devoted to analytical chemistry.

TABLE 1—RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CHEMICAL AND ANALYTICAL CHEMICAL LITERATURE FOR 1970

Country	Analytical literature. % of total chemistry	Relative growth rate. T_a Anal./ T_a Chem.
U. S. S. R.	11.2	1.2
U.S.A.	5.1	0.9
Japan	9.8	0.8
Germany-East & West	6.7	1.2
U. K.	10.3	1.1
France	7.1	1.5
The Netherlands	7.4	1.2
Italy	5.9	0.9
World's literature	8.2	1.0

In the above table, the data in the third column again show that the rate of growth of the analytical

chemistry literature is generally higher than the rate of growth of chemical literature as a whole. The comparatively faster growth of literature in analytical chemistry is again depicted by the concept of 'doubling periods' in Table 2¹².

TABLE 2—DOUBLING TIME (d₂) OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

Discipline	d ₂
^a Analytical chemistry	13.9
^a Chemistry	14.5
^b Biology	16
^b Physics	19
^b Electrical engineering	20
^b Psychology	25
^b Economics	13

India's contribution in the realm of analytical chemistry has always been quite substantial, although a number of recent reports dealing with the growth of different branches of chemistry in this country have tended to ignore this. Starting with the highly significant contribution¹³ to the list of organic reagents by demonstrating the use of dithio-oxamide (rubeanic acid) in 1926 by P. Ray for the detection of copper, cobalt and nickel, the research work in analytical chemistry has continuously progressed in this country and this has been summarised in two reviews^{14,15} upto 1972.

Brooks and Smythe¹⁶ recently reviewed the world progress of analytical chemistry in the period 1910-70. Building upon the previous accounts by Fischer¹⁷ in 1965, these workers compared entries in *Analytical Abstracts* and *Chemical Abstracts* and were able to calculate the percentage of total activity of chemical research in different countries devoted to analytical chemistry (cf., Table 3).

TABLE 3—PERCENTAGE OF ANALYTICAL WORK CARRIED OUT IN VARIOUS COUNTRIES

Country	Year	
	1965	1970
U. S. S. R.	25.4	28.4
U. S. A.	15.8	17.7
Japan	11.0	7.7
Germany	6.4	6.1
U. K.	4.3	5.9
Czechoslovakia	5.3	5.6
France	3.5	2.6
India	3.5	2.1
Scandinavia	0.7	2.0
Romania	3.5	1.8
Poland	4.1	1.5
Spain	1.8	1.3
Netherlands	0.8	1.0
Italy	1.7	-
China	3.1	11.1
Rest of the world	9.1	-

In another analysis of *Analytical Abstracts* published in 1977, Braun and coworkers¹¹ concluded that there were 8311 papers distributed in 741 journals, although there was heavy concentration of 50% and 90% of the papers in only 3% and 36% of the journals respectively. Data for first 50 of the journals are given in Table 4. Two Indian journals, 'Current Indian Journal of Chemistry' and the 'Current Science (India)' are included in this list. These workers further extended their analysis to a 'quality' indicator 'impact factor', which has been defined as the ratio of the number of citations made in any year (say 1978) to the material published in the previous two years (say 1976 and 1977) in a particular journal and the total number of articles published

TABLE 4—THE FIRST 50 LEADING JOURNALS ON ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY COMPUTED FROM ANALYTICAL ABSTRACTS 1977, RANKED BY PRODUCTIVITY

Rank	Journal	No. of papers found	Rank	Journal	No. of papers found
1	J. Chromatogr.	710	26	Rev. Sci. Instr.	52
2	Anal. Chem.	511	27	Lab. Pract.	51
3	Anal. Chim. Acta	338	28	J. Clin. Chem. Clin. Biochem.	51
4	Zh. Anal. Khim.	315	29	Pharmazia	46
5	Anal. Biochem.	300	30	Appl. Spectrosc.	45
6	Fresenius'Z. Anal. Chem.	212	31	Quim. Anal.	40
7	J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.	206	32	Ukr. Khim. Zh.	37
8	Talanta	198	33	Environ. Sci. Technol.	37
9	Bunseki Kagaku Zavod. Lab.	171 170	34	J. Electroanal. Chem.	35
10	Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)	169	35	Interfacial Electrochem.	34
11	Clin. Chem.	161	36	Biochem. Med.	34
12	J. Radioanal. Chem.	147	37	Appl. Opt.	33
13	Analyst	146	38	J. Amer. Oil. Chem. Soc.	33
14	J. Pharm. Sci.	132	39	Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.	32
15	Mikrochim. Acta	116	40	Int. J. Appl. Radiat. Isot.	31
16	Clin. Chim. Acta	109	41	Z. Lebensm. -Unters	31
17	Anal. Lett.	92	42	X-Ray Spectrom.	30
18	Chromatographia	91	43	At. Absorpt. Newsl.	29
19	Radiochem. Radioanal. Lett.	85	44	J. Phys. Sci. Instrum.	29
20	J. Chromatogr. Sci.	76	45	Nucl. Instrum. Methods	29
21	Revista Chim. (Bucharest)	75	46	An. Quim.	28
22	J. Agric. Food. Chem.	71	47	Yukugaku Zasshi	28
23	Indian J. Chem. Sect. A	60	48	(urr. Sci. (India)	28
24	Farmatsiya (Moscow)	52	49	Acta Pol. Pharm.	27
25			50	Z. Chem. (Leipzig)	27
				Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)	27

TABLE 5—IMPACT FACTOR OF LEADING JOURNALS ON ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY (1978)

Rank	Journal	Impact factor	Rank	Journal	Impact factor
1	Clin. Chem.	3.106	21	X-Ray Spectrom	1.118
2	Anal. Chem.	3.058	22	Chem. Pharm. Bull	0.979
3	J. Chromatogr. Sci.	2.586	23	Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.	0.930
4	Anal. Biochem.	2.309	24	J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.	0.916
5	J. Chromatogr.	2.302	25	Int. J. Appl. Radiat. Isot.	0.790
6	Appl. Spectrosc.	2.161	26	J. Phys. Sci. Instrum.	0.714
7	Chromatographia	1.972	27	Mikrochim. Acta	0.697
8	Appl. Opt.	1.934	28	J. Radioanal. Chem.	0.685
9	Clin. Chim. Acta	1.676	29	Radiochem. Radioanal. Lett.	0.639
10	Analyst	1.666	30	Z. Chem. (Leipzig)	0.623
11	J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.	1.525	31	Pharmazie	0.483
12	J. Agric. Food Chem.	1.503	32	Z. Lebensm. Unters. Forsch.	0.455
13	Environ. Sci. Technol.	1.436	33	Bunsek Kagaku	0.410
14	Anal. Chim. Acta	1.404	34	Zh. Anal. Khim.	0.403
15	Anal. Lett.	1.244	35	An. Quim.	0.393
16	Talanta	1.182	36	Indian J. Chem. Sec. A	0.322
17	J. Pharm. Sci.	1.171	37	J. Amer. Oil. Chem. Soc.	0.278
18	J. Clin. Chem. Clin. Biochem.	1.163	38	Acta Pol. Pharm.	0.262
19	Nucl. Instrum. Methods	1.141	39	Curr. Sci. (India)	0.221
20	Rev. Sci. Instr.	1.131	40	Ukr. Khim. Zh.	0.145
			41	Yukugaku Zasshi	0.145
			42	Zavod. Lab.	0.117
			43	Revista Chim. (Bucharest)	0.082

in the same journal during the same two years. The actual data of 1978 impact factors for the top 43 journals are given in Table 5, in which both the Indian journals referred to in Table 4, do find a place albeit very low, almost at the bottom.

Teaching and research in analytical chemistry: Following the more advanced countries, the typical chemistry curriculum adopted by different universities in this country included qualitative group analysis, titrimetric procedures and gravimetric analysis of mixtures including complex materials such as cement, ores and alloys. In addition, courses in analytical aspects of organic analysis were also included at the higher levels. With the changing techniques actually used in analytical operations in academic and industrial laboratories, the curricula have undergone fast changes in developed countries by the introduction of more specialised courses, for example, in electrochemical and spectrochemical analysis, electronics as well as advanced methods of data acquisition and processing.

In view of the above trends, the observation of Herman Liebhafsky in his 1962 Fischer award address, "Like it or not, the chemistry is going out of analytical chemistry", appears to be quite relevant. While one may not agree with this sweeping statement, yet the pressure on the curriculum and available training time tends to make the learners less and less interested in the fundamental aspects of analytical chemistry, the understanding of which remains as essential as ever for practitioners as well as researchers in analytical chemistry.

In the history of analytical chemistry itself, recognition of the fact that analytical chemistry is not solely empirical in nature was only slowly realised. For example, it is only after many decades of 'empirical recommendations' on the temperature at which a precipitate should be heated in a gravimetric procedure that the matter was investigated by Duval and

others in a systematic manner leading to a new branch of study called 'Thermogravimetric Analysis'. The eloquent statement "theory guides, experiment decides" made by the grand analytical chemist of the century, Prof. I. M. Kolthoff is thus continuing to reveal its realism in an ever enhanced manner and hence the task of the teacher in analytical chemistry is becoming all the while more difficult and challenging.

A happy balance between theory and practice in the teaching of analytical chemistry has always been an intricate problem for the framers of curricula and continues to be increasingly so even in the more developed situations. For Universities like ours, the problem becomes even more complex. In the absence of actual sophisticated facilities the extent to which the theoretical features of the same should be taught to enable the learner to use them as these become available to him in later life remains a dilemma for the conscientious teacher, as too much emphasis on theoretical aspects without experimental follow up might give a wrong impression to the learner about the true spirit of this experimental science. Obviously, the resolution of the above dilemma would depend upon the facilities (physical as well as technical) available in any situation, but the following aspects (many of which represent points of special weakness in our system) deserve our special consideration:

- (i) training in instrumentation and fabrication of simple analytical equipments involving glass blowing or knowledge of basic electronics, i.e., inculcation of what is sometimes termed as 'instrumentation culture';
- (ii) a statistical analysis of the experimental data drawing out clearly the 'limits of error' involved in different steps and representing clearly the actual 'precision limits' of the final results. (The extent to which these

steps receive attention in modern analytical chemistry is illustrated by defining clearly the 'guidelines for data acquisition and data quality evaluation' in environment chemistry¹⁸ ;

- (iii) a comparative study of the accuracy of the results obtained by various (classical as well as modern) methods of analysis (the quality of contributions from our laboratories could have been enhanced considerably if this aspect was emphasized in studying the possible interferences as well as in representing the final results in significant figures) ;
- (iv) planning the exercises and problems at the teaching as well as research levels around real life situations rather than basing them only on artificial makeups (a close liaison and cooperation between university laboratories and industrial and other organisations requiring new analytical procedures could be of immense mutual benefit in this direction) ;
- (v) adequate theoretical background and clearer understanding of the basic principles involved in any analytical procedures ;
- (vi) coordination between teaching and research should be encouraged by open ended exercises particularly at the post-graduate level and by formulating problems at the research level from the experiences gained and difficulties faced in such exercises in the teaching laboratories.

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